

Colony sizes, roost use and foraging ecology of *Hipposideros diadema reginae*, a rare bat from tropical Australia

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Hipposideros diadema reginae is a rare subspecies of Diadem Leaf-nosed Bat confined to tropical Queensland. Few data are available on its population size or ecology. From July, 1990 to December, 1993, I conducted colony counts at Chillagoe and Iron Range to assess its abundance, and radio-tagged six males at Chillagoe to provide data on roosting and foraging ecology for management purposes.

I recorded the subspecies in nine of 18 caves surveyed at Chillagoe. Two or more bats were regularly observed in only four caves, each of which had ≥ 250 m of passage, large chambers with high domed ceilings, and multiple entrances. The largest colony was found in Trezkinn Cave (range of 6–65 bats). Both Trezkinn and a nearby cave, Donna, were fully developed tourist caves, but were frequently used as day roosts by radio-tagged bats. Each cave had a gate at its entrance. At Iron Range, between 70 and 250 bats roosted in Gordon's Mine.

Bats used multiple day roosts, but did not change roost every day. The main foraging behaviour was perch hunting, with continuous flight as a secondary behaviour. The mean foraging range of tagged bats was 1.08 km from the day roost (range of 0.3–2.5 km). Foraging occurred within all available types of vegetation; use of vegetation showed intraspecific variation.

Hipposideros d. reginae exhibits flexibility in its foraging ecology, but has specific roost requirements. Recommended management actions are: prevent or regulate human access to roosts, search for additional colonies at Chillagoe by targeting potentially suitable caves, and ban scientific collecting at both sites.

Key words: *Hipposideros diadema reginae*, Cave-dwelling bats, Roost management, Foraging ecology, Habitat.

INTRODUCTION

THE Diadem Leaf-nosed Bat *Hipposideros diadema* is a large species (32–57 g) which occurs in the Old World tropics from Burma and Thailand through south-east Asia to New Guinea and northern Australia (Corbet and Hill 1991). Currently 18 subspecies are generally recognized within this range. However, a number of subspecies may be given full species status in the future (Kitchener *et al.* 1992). In Australia, *H. diadema* occurs as two disjunct populations; *H. d. reginae* in north Queensland, and *H. d. inornata* in the Top End of the Northern Territory (Koopman 1984). Both subspecies are confined to Australia (Kitchener *et al.* 1992).

Hipposideros d. reginae occurs along the east coast of Cape York Peninsula south to about Townsville and as far inland as Chillagoe. Little is known about its ecology. Individuals have been observed to capture prey by perch hunting, whereby they hang from a tree limb and fly out to catch passing insects (Brown and Berry 1989; Fenton 1982). Echolocation calls are emitted at frequencies of 55–58 kHz and contain a long constant frequency component (Brown and Berry 1989; Hall and Richards 1985; Fenton 1982). The diet consists mostly of hard-bodied insects, with small vertebrates taken occasionally (Pavey and Burwell 1997).

Hipposideros d. reginae is listed as rare under Queensland Government legislation (*Nature*

Conservation Legislation Amendment Regulation (No. 2) 1997). The conservation status of the subspecies is of concern because it roosts in caves and disused mines (Hall *et al.* 1997; Hall and Richards 1995). Destruction of mines as a result of reworking, entrance collapse or deliberate closure for health and safety reasons, and human disturbance of caves and mines are major threats faced by cave-dwelling bats (Hall *et al.* 1997). The subspecies is known to be extremely sensitive to human disturbance (Hall *et al.* 1997). A further threatening process faced by all bat species is the loss of foraging habitat (Jones *et al.* 1995). A lack of data on colony sizes, and roosting and foraging ecology of *H. d. reginae* make it very difficult to assess its response to the threatening processes listed above.

From July, 1990 to December, 1993, I conducted a study of *H. d. reginae* at two sites, Chillagoe and Iron Range, where known roosts occur. My aims were to obtain baseline data on the size of colonies, and to gain an understanding of its roosting and foraging ecology. Such data will be of importance in developing management guidelines for *H. d. reginae* at the two sites.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study areas

The study areas were the Chillagoe-Mungana karst system centred on the town of Chillagoe

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PACIFIC CONSERVATION BIOLOGY Vol. 4: 232–39. Surrey Beatty & Sons, Sydney. 1998.

(17°09'S, 144°31'E), and Lamond Hill at Iron Range (12°43'S, 143°18'E). The rainfall is highly seasonal at both sites with distinct wet (December to April) and dry (May to November) periods. Vegetation at Chillagoe (300–450 m a.s.l.) includes deciduous vine thicket, a type of dry rainforest which grows on limestone outcrops; open forest, which is mostly confined to drainage lines; and woodland, which occurs on footslopes, plains and terraces (Godwin 1991). Iron Range (0–200 m a.s.l.) has a complex mosaic of vegetation types, but is dominated by semi-deciduous mesophyll vine thicket and evergreen notophyll vine forest (Lavarack and Godwin 1987).

Colony counts

At Chillagoe, 18 caves were surveyed at least once during eight excursions from July, 1990 to December, 1993 (Table 1). None of the surveyed caves was used as a maternity roost. During each survey I searched all accessible areas of a cave for roosting bats. I identified *H. d. reginae* by its large size and patches of pale fur on the body, a feature not observed in other Australian bats (Hall and Richards 1995). I surveyed Gordon's Mine, a disused gold mine at Iron Range, during five excursions from November 1990 to July 1993. Pregnant females roosted in the mine in late November of 1990 and 1992 (Pavey, pers. obs.), but it is not known if they gave birth there.

Counts at both locations were conducted during three periods of the year (Table 2); wet season (December, February, March), early dry season (June, July) and late dry season

(November). I counted *H. d. reginae* using the direct count method described in Thomas and La Val (1988). Counts at Gordon's Mine for each survey period are presented as a range, because numbers were estimated to avoid undue disturbance of the colony. At Chillagoe, I was able to count all the individuals present in each cave.

Radio-tracking

I attached transmitters to six males (mass: 44.0–57.0 g, forearm: 78.9–84.2 mm) at Chillagoe and two females (mass: 41.8–46.5 g, forearm: 80.3 mm) at Iron Range. Bats were captured using hand-nets and mist-nets at their day roosts. At Chillagoe, I did not catch bats in caves where the risk of disturbance was high, rather I captured bats roosting alone away from the main roosts. All bats captured by this method were males.

All bats tagged at Chillagoe were captured in caves on a limestone outcrop called Donna Tower during two periods in the dry season of 1993, June–July (bats 1 and 2, Table 3) and November–December (bats 3 to 6, Table 3). Bats were tracked for a combined total of 146.9 h over 23 bat nights (Table 3). Bats were tracked at Iron Range in July 1993 for three nights. However, bats foraged only in rainforest where the reception range was very low and accurate fixes were difficult to obtain, so I discontinued the Iron Range study and discarded the data.

I used single stage transmitters (0.99–1.07 g, Titley Electronics, Ballina, Australia) that were <4% of each bat's body mass, thus being below

Table 1. Physical characteristics and human use of roosts surveyed for *H. d. reginae*. Gordon's Mine is at Iron Range, whereas all other sites are at Chillagoe. Cave data based on Chillagoe Caving Club (1982). Roosts from which the subspecies was recorded prior to the study are marked in bold.

Roost	No. chambers	Length of passage (m)	Human use
Gordon's Mine	0	>90	Regularly explored by tourists, specimens collected since 1948
Donna Cave	2	250	Fully developed tourist cave, gate at entrance
Trezkinn Cave	2	400	Fully developed tourist cave, gate at entrance, bat research September 1980
Royal Arch Cave	25	3 000	Fully developed tourist cave, gate at entrance
Bauhinia Cave	1	40	Self-guided tourist cave
Pompeii Cave	0	<50	Self-guided tourist cave
Carpentaria Cave	10	1 500	Self-guided tourist cave
Royal Archway Cave	2	<100	Self-guided tourist cave
Haunted Cave	3	400	Self-guided tourist cave
Ryan Imperial Cave	5	200	Former tourist cave, gate at entrance
Pink's Cave	1	50	Non-tourist, historically popular cave
Surprise Cave	1	60	Non-tourist, historically popular cave
Brief Hole	2	<100	Non-tourist, historically popular cave
Ryan's Creek Cave	>2	300	Non-tourist, bat research August 1980, seven specimens collected August 1980
Kiwi Cave	3	30	Non-tourist, bat research September 1980
Tea Tree Cave	3	300	Non-tourist, archaeological site
Hennesy's Cave	1	40	Non-tourist
The Rat Hole	1	?	Non-tourist
Masonic Cavern	2	?	Non-tourist

the 5% threshold for which transmitters may affect bat flight (Aldridge and Brigham 1988). The two bats tracked at Chillagoe in June-July also had a light-tag attached for one night. The light-tag was a glass bulb filled with a cold chemical called Cyalume (American Cyanamid, Milton, Florida, USA). The combined mass of the light-tag and radio-tag was less than 5% of the body mass of each bat. By tracking the light-tagged bats, I could both observe the behaviours which produced particular signals from the radio-tag and determine how signal strength changed with proximity to the bat.

My radio-tracking methodology was very similar to that of Jones and Morton (1992). Several bats had transmitters attached at any one time, but only one individual was chosen as the target bat. This bat was continuously tracked for the entire night from dusk (1830 h to 1930 h) till after dawn (0500 h to 0600 h) or until its signal was lost. If contact with the target bat was lost, another bat was tracked.

Each bat was tracked with a Regal 2000 receiver and a hand-held antenna (Titley Electronics) by a team of at least two observers. One observer operated the tracking equipment while the other observer(s) recorded behaviour and movements on a mini cassette tape recorder, navigated, and drove the vehicle. If the bat remained close to its day roost, observers tracked it on foot. However, if the bat moved away from the roost, observers did not attempt to determine its flight path, but they tracked it from a 4WD vehicle until the bat commenced foraging. A 4WD vehicle was essential to allow off road access to the rugged terrain at Chillagoe. The precise location of a foraging or perching bat was determined by circling the area from which a signal was received on foot (the "homing-in" method of White and Garrott 1990). Surveyors tape was attached to the trunks of trees in or near which bats foraged. Sites identified as foraging areas were revisited during daylight to identify vegetation types and other components of the habitat.

The behaviour of a target bat was monitored once it departed the day roost. Behaviour during the night was classified as one of four types. 1) Perching. A bat was perched in a tree or shrub. Often this behaviour involved perch hunting, whereby the bat actively echolocated. Sometimes it made short flights to capture prey or to move to another perch, but these flights were of shorter duration than the time spent perched. 2) Continuous flight. A bat foraged while flying over a small area; perching, if recorded, was for a shorter duration than the time spent flying. 3) Other flight. A bat was in commuting flight (direct, fast flight) or flight with an unknown function. 4) Night roosting. A

bat was considered to be night roosting when it perched in a cave between bouts of flight.

Four vegetation types were present within a 3 600 ha area at Chillagoe within which tagged bats foraged. The percentage of this area occupied by each vegetation type was estimated by placing a grid (0.2 cm squares) over aerial photographs and designating each square according to the vegetation that covered most of the square.

RESULTS

Colony sizes

Hipposideros d. reginae was observed in 9 of 18 caves (50%) surveyed at Chillagoe (Table 2), six of which it was known from previously (Table 1). The occupied caves were of three types: 1) fully developed tourist caves, in which guided tours were run daily and which had electric lights, protective barriers, hand rails and fully formed pathways; 2) self-guided tourist caves, undeveloped caves which were advertised in a Queensland National Parks and Wildlife Service brochure, and which were signposted so tourists could explore them at their own pace; and 3) non-tourist caves, undeveloped caves which were not advertised or signposted.

Trezkinn Cave was the only roost surveyed at Chillagoe which supported ≥ 10 *H. d. reginae* during any count (Table 2), although numbers varied considerably between survey periods with a range of 6–65 (Table 2). Two or more individuals were regularly observed in only three other caves; Donna, Carpentaria and Ryan's Creek. Each of these caves contained ≥ 250 m of passage, had multiple chambers with high domed ceilings, and multiple entrances (Table 1). Typical roosts were in large domed chambers, up to 20 m high, in which bats hung from the chamber ceiling.

At Iron Range, the colony size in Gordon's Mine ranged from 70 to 250 bats during 1990–1993. A maximum count of 250 was made in July, 1992; however, a range of 70–100 bats was more typical (Table 2). The subspecies was not found in several nearby mines nor in other artificial roosts (e.g., concrete bunkers, culverts, wooden bridges) occupied by other bat species.

Roost use and activity patterns

Of the four roosts at Chillagoe which regularly held ≥ 2 *H. d. reginae*, Donna and Trezkinn Caves are located on Donna Tower, a 400 m long limestone outcrop where the six radio-tagged bats were captured. Other caves on the tower which I surveyed were Bauhinia, Pompeii, Surprise, Brief Hole, The Rat Hole, and Masonic Cavern (Table 1). All tagged bats,

Table 2. Counts of *H. d. reginae* at Gordon's Mine, Iron Range and at caves at Chillagoe during 1990–1993.

Roost	Survey period								
	July 1990	Nov. 1990	Dec. 1991	June 1992	July 1992	Nov. 1992	Feb./Mar. 1993	June/July 1993	Nov. 1993
Gordon's Mine	—	70–100	—	—	≥250	70–100	70–100	100–120	—
Donna Cave	—	—	5	3	3	1	4	0	1
Royal Arch Cave	—	—	—	0	—	—	1	0	1
Trezkinn Cave	44	—	6	19	9	65	65	35	43
Pompeii Cave	0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1
Carpentaria Cave	2	—	1	—	—	—	6	1	4
Surprise Cave	—	—	0	—	0	—	0	2	1
Ryan's Creek Cave	1	—	1	4	2	5	7	4	5
Bauhinia Cave	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1
Masonic Cavern	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	1

except number 3, continued to day roost on Donna Tower for at least one day after capture. The bats used five caves as day roosts; Donna, Trezkinn, Surprise, Bauhinia, and Pompeii, of which Donna and Trezkinn were the most frequently used (Table 4). Bats used multiple day roosts, but did not change roost every day. For example, bat 5 roosted in Trezkinn Cave on seven consecutive days. Bats also used multiple night roosts (Table 4), which were located in Trezkinn, Donna and Bauhinia Caves.

Target bats were tracked for the complete night on 14 occasions. These bats had one ($n = 6$) or several activity periods a night (five nights of two activity periods, two nights of three periods, and one night of five periods). The mean time $\pm$ SE spent outside the roost for these bats was 221.93 ± 25.17 mins per night ($n = 14$). The activity rhythm of bat 5 showed two peaks, one between 1900 h and 2300 h, and the other between 0300 h and 0600 h (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. The percentage of time each hour (over seven nights) during which a radio-tagged *H. d. reginae* (bat 5) was active and night roosting.

No activity was recorded between 2300 h and 0200 h. During this period, last light was at about 1930 h and first light at about 0445 h.

Foraging behaviour

Perching was the main behaviour recorded outside the roost (Table 3). Perching usually involved perch hunting, whereby a bat hung from a tree or shrub while actively echolocating and flew out to intercept flying insects. Occasionally it was not possible to determine whether a perched bat was hunting or resting. Because of this difficulty, the behaviours are referred to as "perching" in Table 3. Five of the six tagged bats also foraged during continuous flight (Table 3), during which a bat detected and captured insects while it was flying. However, this behaviour was rare compared to perching (Table 3).

Foraging areas

Tagged bats had between one and three distinct foraging areas (Table 4). Those individuals with multiple areas foraged in more than one during any given night. For example, bat 1 used all three of its foraging areas during the night of 1 July. Bat 5, which was tracked for eight nights (Table 3), had a single foraging area (Table 4).

Foraging areas were generally close to the day roosts of tagged bats. The foraging range (i.e., straight line distance from the day roost to the furthest point travelled) was calculated for those nights when both the target bat was in contact for an entire night and the location of its day roost was known. The mean foraging range $\pm$ SE for bats 1, 2, 5 and 6 combined was 1.08 ± 0.20 km ($n = 12$ nights), with a range of 0.3–2.5 km. The mean foraging range for bat 5, which was tracked for the most nights, was 0.83 km ($n = 6$ nights), with a range of 0.3–1.0 km.

Foraging habitat

Tagged bats at Chillagoe foraged in woodland, open forest, deciduous vine thicket and within

Table 3. Summary of data on the behaviour of *H. d. reginae* at Chillagoe showing cumulative time in minutes spent on each of four activities by radio-tagged bats. The percentage of time spent by a bat on each behaviour is given in brackets.

Bat number	Nights (n)	Total time	Perching	Continuous flight	Other flight	Night roost
1	5	1 521	401 (27)	36 (2)	62 (4)	1 022 (67)
2	2	743	209 (28)	0	20 (3)	514 (69)
3	3	1 157	1 122 (97)	35 (3)	0	0
4	1	351	336 (96)	4 (1)	11 (3)	0
5	8	3 707	971 (26)	192 (5)	64 (2)	2 480 (67)
6	4	1 333	343 (26)	33.5 (2)	26.5 (2)	930 (70)
Total	23	8 812	3 382	300.5	183.5	4 946

Table 4. Night and day roosts and foraging areas of radio-tagged *H. d. reginae* at Chillagoe.

Parameter	Bat number					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
No. of day roosts (No. of days)	3 (6)	2 (2)	1 (1)	1 (1)	3 (9)	2 (3)
No. days at Trezkinn Cave	4	0	0	0	7	0
No. days at Donna Cave	1	1	1	0	1	2
No. of night roosts	2	1	—	—	3	2
No. of foraging areas	3	1	1	2	1	2

Fig. 2. Availability of vegetation types in the study area and percentage of foraging time spent in each vegetation type by radio-tagged *H. d. reginae* at Chillagoe.

the town of Chillagoe (Fig. 2). The percentage of the study area taken up by each vegetation type was: 8% deciduous vine thicket, 2% open forest, 87% woodland, and 3% human settlement, including the town of Chillagoe. The pattern of occupation of vegetation during foraging showed considerable variation among the six bats (Fig. 2). Four bats foraged predominantly in woodland, one bat predominantly in open forest, and the other bat predominantly in vine thicket. Bats 1 and 5 foraged within the town of Chillagoe.

Five foraging bouts, four of perch hunting and one of continuous flight, were seen in sufficient detail to observe the use of habitat components. Foraging flights were observed at the edge of vegetation and small clearings ($n = 3$) and in woodland with a canopy cover of about 30% ($n = 2$). Flights were always in open space (>0.5 m from vegetation). Three hunting perches ranged from 4 to 5 m above the ground, and all were within 5 to 10 cm of the end of leafless twigs with a diameter of 2–5 mm. Perches were below the lowest leaves of the

crown foliage. Bats flew out from perches into open space to intercept passing insects. Bat 2 used the same perch on a branch on consecutive nights.

DISCUSSION

Colony sizes

Low numbers of *H. d. reginae* occupied the roosts surveyed at Chillagoe and Iron Range during 1990–1993. Only Trezkinn Cave and Gordon's Mine had counts of ≥ 10 individuals (Table 2). Although 9 of 18 caves at Chillagoe contained the subspecies, only four caves consistently held ≥ 2 individuals. My results indicate that the combined population size of roosts at Chillagoe and Gordon's Mine during 1990–1993 was at most 350 individuals. This estimate is of concern, because I targeted known roosts of *H. d. reginae*. I knew of 13 caves at Chillagoe from which it had been recorded up to 1990 (Chillagoe Caving Club 1982, 1990; D. Flett, Queensland National Parks and Wildlife Service, unpubl. data; CSIRO Australian National Wildlife Collection, unpubl. data), nine of which I surveyed. Over 500 caves occur within the Chillagoe-Mungana karst system, and large colonies may occur among other caves. However, many of these caves have been explored by cavers who are competent in bat identification, yet the subspecies was rarely sighted (Chillagoe Caving Club 1982, 1990). Further, the apparent preference of *H. d. reginae* for large caves with large chambers and multiple entrances indicates that suitable roosts may be limited.

Hipposideros d. reginae appears to be one of the rarer subspecies of *H. diadema* (Hall and Richards 1995). By comparison, *H. d. griseus* and *H. d. masoni* from mainland New Guinea and peninsular Malaysia, respectively, are both common and frequently recorded in caves (Flannery 1995; Medway 1983). Likewise, *H. d. oceanitis* was found in "great abundance" in nearly all the caves and tunnels visited by Smith and Hood (1981) on New Ireland and New Britain.

Human visitation to roosts

My colony counts indicate a decline in numbers at two roosts since the early 1980s. Ryan's Creek Cave held a maximum of seven *H. d. reginae* during 1990–1993 (Table 2), whereas 120 bats were observed in August–September, 1980 (Hall and Richards 1985). Gordon's Mine had a maximum of 250 bats during 1990–1993 (Table 2), but estimates from September, 1981 indicate that between 600 and several thousand were present (S. Churchill, P. Helman, L. Hall, pers. comm.).

The cause of the decline at Ryan's Creek Cave is not known. The decline at Gordon's Mine may have been caused by human disturbance. Human visitation to Iron Range underwent a large increase between the early 1980s and 1993 (M. Geyle, Queensland National Parks and Wildlife Service, pers. comm.). Gordon's Mine is within 200 m of a popular camp site and was regularly explored by tourists during 1990–1993 (Pavey, pers. obs.). Disturbance probably led to bats using other roosts. Other subspecies of *H. diadema* are known to roost in the forest canopy (McKean 1972) and in tree hollows (Flannery 1995; Medway 1983), so the bats from Gordon's Mine may have done likewise. The high level of human disturbance to Gordon's Mine resulted in a gate being placed at its entrance in late March 1998 (B. Thomson, Queensland National Parks and Wildlife Service, pers. comm.).

Two fully developed tourist caves, Trezkinn and Donna, were frequently used as day roosts by tagged bats at Chillagoe (Table 4). Trezkinn Cave held the largest colony of the 18 caves surveyed and Donna Cave was also an important roost. Both caves were accessible to the public only during tours which ran for 30 and 60–90 mins daily at Trezkinn and Donna Caves, respectively. Locked gates prevented human access at other times.

Roost use and activity patterns

An intermediate level of roost site fidelity was exhibited by tagged bats at Chillagoe. Individuals had multiple day roosts (Table 4), but they used a single roost for multiple days. Among bats, high roost availability (e.g., foliage roosting) is negatively associated with roost fidelity, whereas high roost permanency (e.g., cave roosting) is positively associated with roost fidelity (Lewis 1995). Tagged *H. d. reginae* occupied roosts on Donna Tower which were both permanent and readily available, which may explain their intermediate level of roost fidelity.

Bats at Chillagoe typically had one or two foraging bouts per night. Three or more activity periods per night were less common. Multiple foraging bouts interspersed by periods of night roosting are characteristic of the activity patterns of other rhinolophoid bats including the Greater Horseshoe Bat *Rhinolophus ferrumequinum* (Jones and Morton 1992), Rufous Horseshoe Bat *R. rouxi* (Neuweiler *et al.* 1987), and Ghost Bat *Macroderma gigas* (Tidemann *et al.* 1985).

Foraging ecology

Tagged bats at Chillagoe showed flexibility in their use of foraging behaviour and vegetation types. *Hipposideros d. reginae* is similar to other rhinolophoid bats in foraging both by perch

hunting and continuous flight (Jones and Morton 1992; Neuweiler *et al.* 1987; Fenton and Rautenbach 1986). However, perch hunting was the dominant foraging behaviour of my study animals both during June-July and November-December (Table 3). Both light-tagged and radio-tagged bats at Chillagoe in August-September, 1980 foraged only by perch hunting (Brown and Berry 1989; Fenton 1982).

Bats foraged in all vegetation types available at Chillagoe and showed intraspecific variation in use of vegetation (Fig. 2). Some individuals foraged in a single vegetation type, whereas others occupied up to three types. Although bats exhibited flexibility in use of vegetation, they appeared to require the same habitat components within each vegetation type. Typical foraging sites were at the edge of or within gaps in stands of vegetation, where leafless twigs adjacent to open space were used as hunting perches. Such foraging habitat is reported for *H. diadema* from throughout its range including New Britain (Smith and Hood 1981), Timor (Goodwin 1979), and peninsular Malaysia (Heller and Volleth 1989). In rainforest in north Queensland, it is considered to be a gap specialist (Crome and Richards 1988). The ability to forage in gaps may enable *H. diadema* to persist in rainforest after selective logging (Zubaid 1993).

Tagged bats had between one and three foraging areas, which were all located close to their day roosts. The subspecies exhibited intraspecific variation with respect to foraging site fidelity; one bat had a single foraging area over eight nights, whereas another occupied three discrete areas during a single night. The use of multiple foraging areas and intraspecific variation in foraging site fidelity has been reported for several species of insectivorous bats (Wethington *et al.* 1996; Clark *et al.* 1993; Jones and Morton 1992; Tidemann *et al.* 1985).

The average foraging range of *H. d. reginae* was 1.08 km with a range of 0.3–2.5 km. This distance is smaller than that recorded for radio-tagged and light-tagged individuals of most species of insectivorous bats studied to date (Jones *et al.* 1995). However, a few species have similar foraging ranges to *H. d. reginae*. For example, 16 Brown Long-eared Bats *Plecotus auritus*, radio tagged in north-east Scotland spent 60% of total flight time within 0.5 km of the roost, and 92% of flight time within 1.5 km of the roost. The maximum distance travelled by an individual from the roost was 2.8 km (Entwhistle *et al.* 1996).

Foraging range does vary with reproductive state. Among the reproductive classes of *R. ferrumequinum*, post-lactating females had a mean foraging range of 4.03 km ($n = 3$ nights),

whereas that of sub-adult males was 2.31 km ($n = 14$ nights) (Jones *et al.* 1995). In contrast, the maximum foraging range of adult male *P. auritus* was greater than that for all female reproductive classes (Entwhistle *et al.* 1996). Such variation suggests that the foraging range I calculated for *H. d. reginae* is only applicable to adult males.

MANAGEMENT RECOMMENDATIONS

Management efforts should concentrate on preventing or regulating human access to roosts of *H. d. reginae*. Gordon's Mine, Iron Range, should be regularly monitored following gate placement in March, 1998, both to examine colony trends and to ensure physical conditions in the mine do not deteriorate. Human access to caves such as Surprise, Bauhinia, and Pompeii on Donna Tower, Chillagoe, should be prevented if possible, or, at the very least, these caves should no longer be promoted as self-guiding tourist caves. Further surveys should be conducted in the Chillagoe-Mungana karst system to determine the status of *H. d. reginae* in the area. Surveys should target relatively large caves with multiple entrances and large chambers. Scientific collection should not be permitted at any roost of *H. d. reginae* at either location.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I wish to thank Les Hall for encouraging me to understand the management implications of ecological research. The work presented here formed part of my Ph.D. thesis supervised by Gimme Walter and Les Hall. I thank Greg Richards, Mick Godwin, David Flett, and Bruce Thomson for providing advice and information which was greatly appreciated. I thank Boris Saraber, Amos Saraber, Danny Chew, Ken Cross, Damian Milne, Mark Newton, Tim Perry, and Michael Ross for energetic field assistance. Financial assistance was provided by the Royal Zoological Society of New South Wales, Linnean Society of New South Wales, Australian Geographic Society, Ecological Society of Australia, Wet Tropics Management Authority, M. A. Ingram Trust, The University of Queensland, and a Priority Australian Postgraduate Research Award. I am very grateful for the logistic support provided by Queensland National Parks and Wildlife Service staff at Chillagoe and Iron Range, and by Luke Leung and Marina Kenway at Lockhart River. Necessary permits and ethics approval were granted by the Queensland Department of Environment and Heritage and the Animal Experimentation and Ethics Committee of The University of Queensland. Constructive comments on earlier versions of the manuscript were provided by Brad Law and three anonymous referees.

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